

Carbon storage potential of wood and biochar in global urban building scenarios

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Abstract

Urbanization is accelerating globally, increasing material demand and associated greenhouse gas emissions. Bio-based construction materials can enable long-term carbon storage in buildings, yet their mitigation potential, interaction with circular strategies, and feasibility remain uncertain. Here, we assess carbon storage in global urban building stocks under future scenarios, focusing on two material strategies, structural wood and biochar-based concrete, while accounting for associated emission outcomes and feasibility considerations.

We find that substituting conventional construction systems with structural wood in 50% of new urban buildings could increase carbon storage by $0.4 \text{ GtCO}_2 \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (+173%) by 2050 relative to a current-practice baseline, with the largest contributions in rapidly urbanizing regions of Asia and Africa. In contrast, large-scale adoption of biochar-based concrete yields only a 12% increase in carbon storage by 2050, constrained by limited feasible substitution rates in cement. Over 2020–2100, structural wood substitution could reduce cumulative embodied emissions from urban construction by up to 46%, compared to only 2% for biochar-based concrete. Combining material substitutions with sufficiency and circular strategies that reduce overall material demand delivers the greatest mitigation potential, lowering cumulative net embodied emissions by up to 57% for wood and 38% for biochar. However, achieving the full carbon storage potentials requires significant supply expansion, up to a factor 1.75 for wood and more than twenty-five-fold for biochar compared without circular strategies. These findings clarify the potential, limits, and feasibility of bio-based carbon storage in urban buildings worldwide.

Keywords:

Carbon sequestration, Cities, Building sector modelling, Bio-based materials, Material efficiency, Climate change mitigation, Scenario analysis

Introduction

Urban areas are responsible for approximately 70% of global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (Rhodium Group 2024, Ge and Friedrich 2024); the building and land transport sectors alone accounting for roughly 6–13% and 12–16% of global emissions respectively, depending on whether indirect electricity-related emissions are included (Rhodium Group 2024, Ge and Friedrich 2024). Ongoing urbanization adds pressure: the global urban population is projected to grow by over two billion by 2050, predominantly in cities of the Global South, which in turn translates into new construction and transport infrastructure expansion (UN 2022). The long lifespans of buildings (>40 years) and transport infrastructure (often exceeding a century) mean that investment and planning decisions made today will lock in emissions trajectories for decades (Creutzig *et al* 2016). Hence, urban infrastructure choices are structurally decisive for global climate solutions. For example, compact, well-connected cities offering mitigation potential of 27–57% in buildings and transport relative to sprawling counterparts (Creutzig *et al* 2016). Yet urbanization in many rapidly growing regions continues to follow low-density, material intensive patterns that relate to high GHG emissions both by provision and by usage (spatial lock-in) (IPCC 2022b). The current wave of urbanization must therefore be managed not only in terms of overall demand but also via material strategies to reduce or compensate emissions (Dunant *et al* 2025).

Buildings are responsible for 21% of global GHG emissions due to their operation and construction (Cabeza *et al* 2022), requiring urgent mitigation action. Global life cycle emissions from the buildings and construction sector could increase by ~50% to nearly twofold by mid-century if no further action is taken (Li *et al* 2025, Zhong *et al* 2021). More than half of these emissions are expected to come from materials, or embodied emissions (UNEP 2023, Röck *et al* 2020). Although decarbonizing the supply-side of materials has been thoroughly investigated, sufficiency and circular strategies can significantly reduce embodied emissions and might even be required for meeting climate goals (Alaux, *et al* 2026, Mastrucci *et al* 2023).

Buildings play an important role for carbon dioxide removal and storage (CDR) strategies (Maierhofer *et al* 2023), due to their relatively long lifetime. Previous studies estimate that switching to wood-based construction could result in a storage potential of buildings up to 1.32 Gt CO₂ yr⁻¹ globally (Mishra *et al* 2022). A broader set of construction-related materials, including biochar-based concrete and bricks with bio-fibers, hold a storage potential of up to 16.6 Gt CO₂ yr⁻¹ globally, based on current production levels (Van Roijen *et al* 2025). Two main processes contribute to the CDR potential of buildings: carbon uptake and long-term carbon storage. Both wood- and biochar-based materials are locking biogenic carbon from their feedstock for as long as the material remains intact and is not incinerated, functioning as carbon sink when coupled with reforestation (Zhou *et al* 2025, Abed *et al* 2022). Biochar's high porosity and surface area also allow it to continue sequestering carbon after production (Zhou *et al* 2025). Structural wood, by contrast, does not actively sequester carbon after processing; however, bio-based residues from production and construction, as well as deadstock and end-of-life material, can serve as feedstock for biochar production (Zhou *et al* 2025, Abed *et al* 2022). For both material types, photosynthesis during tree growth forms the foundation of carbon storage, meaning CDR potential can only be realized when harvested stands are reforested (Rodriguez Mendez *et al* 2024). Beyond direct carbon storage, lower embodied emissions – achievable through sufficiency and circular strategies (Hertwich *et al* 2019, Pauliuk *et al* 2021, Zhong *et al* 2021) – further contribute to the overall climate mitigation potential of construction materials (Xue *et al* 2024). Circular strategies such as material reuse and wood cascading can extend this potential by avoiding the emissions associated with virgin material production (Abed *et al* 2022).

Despite recent assessments of the carbon storage potential in the global building sector, significant limitations remain. Most existing scenarios focus primarily on structural wood (Mishra *et al* 2022, Churkina *et al* 2020, Gingrich *et al* 2025, Yayla *et al* 2025), whereas information on other materials is

limited. Current estimates of storage potential for a broader set of materials largely rely on present-day production of conventional materials (Van Roijen *et al* 2025), with insufficient consideration of future material demand, interactions with the supply-side, and feasibility constraints. Moreover, knowledge of potential trade-offs and synergies with other sufficiency and circular strategies remains limited (Gingrich *et al* 2025, Vélez-Henao and Pauliuk 2025). On the other hand, integrated assessment models (IAMs) used to assess long-term mitigation scenarios generally lack the granularity to adequately represent these sectoral strategies, and often depend on critical simplifications and assumptions (Wiedenhofer *et al* 2024, Pauliuk *et al* 2017). Enhancing the representation of carbon storage and circular strategies in the global building sector is essential to more accurately assess their realistic potential in future mitigation efforts.

Here, we explore scenarios implementing structural wood and biochar-based concrete as carbon storage strategies in the global urban building sector. Our analysis accounts for associated carbon emissions and storage potential, synergies and trade-offs with sufficiency and circular strategies, and feasibility considerations by comparison with current production levels of different materials. We use the detailed global IAM-based building stock model MESSAGEix-Buildings (Mastrucci *et al* 2021), combined with Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), to generate projections of future material demand, carbon storage potential, and embodied emissions associated with building construction. These scenarios aim to inform realistic mitigation and sustainability scenarios for urban buildings worldwide.

Methods

Our modelling framework to assess global urban scenarios integrates the building stock model MESSAGEix-Buildings, sectoral extension to the MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM IAM (Mastrucci *et al* 2021), and LCA for carbon storage and embodied emission estimations accounting for material supply chains. The following sections describe building stock modelling, carbon storage potential and emission accounting, and scenario setup.

Building stock modelling

MESSAGEix-Buildings is a building stock model that assesses buildings-related energy and material flows in future scenarios, embedding a stock-turnover model based on dynamic material flow analysis (MFA). The model covers both residential and non-residential buildings globally and has high granularity in representing heterogeneous building characteristics across geographical regions and locations. The model runs for 61 regions globally – aggregated here to 6 regions (see Supplementary Information, section 1) for results reporting – with five-year timesteps until 2060, and ten-year timesteps until 2100. At every time step, the model calculates the size of the stock, number of demolitions based on building type-specific survival curves, and number of new constructions to replace demolished buildings and meet population-driven demand (Fishman *et al* 2024). The size of the building stock, expressed in housing unit for residential and floor space for non-residential, is driven by population growth in different regions. Urban population projections are based on total population and urbanization projections for the Shared Socio-economic Pathway SSP2 (Riahi *et al* 2017, Kc and Lutz 2017, Jiang and O’Neill 2017). For residential buildings, floor space is calculated by applying a share of different housing types (single-family housing and multi-family housing) in different regions, and floor space per capita by housing type (Mastrucci *et al* 2021). Floor space per capita in non-residential buildings is GDP-dependent (Harvey 2014), and estimated using GDP projections for SSP2 (Dellink *et al* 2017). We calculate material inflows by multiplying newly constructed floor area by material intensity coefficients representing different building types, construction types, and region from the RASMI database (Fishman *et al* 2024). The set of materials in this study include aluminum, bricks, concrete, copper, glass, steel, and wood. In addition, we consider material variants for structural wood and biochar-based concrete representing new construction technologies (see Supplementary Information, sections 2-3, for input data description).

Carbon storage potential and emission accounting

We apply biogenic carbon content of structural wood materials and biochar carbon content in concrete applications to assess the carbon stock change dynamics in the global urban building carbon pool through 2100. Stock increase in structural wood and biochar-based concrete results in additional carbon storage.. Carbon storage intensities are estimated at 2.93 kg CO₂/kg for biochar (Zhou *et al* 2026), corresponding to 0.011 kg CO₂/kg for biochar-based concrete (see Supplementary Information, section 4), and at 1.833 kg CO₂/kg for sawnwood (Rüter *et al* 2019). We run additional sensitivity analyses to account for the range of values for carbon storage potential based on the literature (see Supplementary Information, section 4). We quantify embodied emissions for the set of seven construction materials above using prospective LCA data based on a previous study (Zhong *et al* 2021). The analysis of embodied emissions draws on the ecoinvent 3.6 database (Wernet *et al* 2016) and accounts for shifts in energy mixes and technologies aligned with a reference SSP2 current policy scenario.

Scenarios

The scenario framing combines two sets of strategies, namely material substitution and material efficiency, for a total of nine combined scenarios (Table 1). We explore two material substitution strategies considering materials with high carbon storage potential (Van Roijen *et al* 2025) for new urban buildings: biochar-based concrete (*Biochar* scenario) and structural wood (*Wood* scenario). We assume ambitious substitution levels of conventional technologies up to 50% by 2050 for both strategies, similar to other studies on wood substitution (Mishra *et al* 2022, Mastrucci *et al* 2024). The material substitution scenarios are contrasted with a scenario assuming continuation of current construction practice (*Current practice* scenario).

We combine these scenarios with a set of material efficiency scenarios to investigate the trade-offs and synergies with floorspace per capita reduction in new buildings (*Sufficiency* scenario) and a range of circular strategies (*Circular* scenario), including lifetime extension, lightweighting, and increased use of recycled materials, besides floorspace per capita reduction. These two scenarios are compared with a scenario assuming continuation of current trends and practices (*Reference* scenario). All scenarios share the same socio-demographic development consistent with the SSP2 storyline (O’Neill *et al* 2017).

Table 1 Scenarios overview.

Scenario name	Description
Material substitution scenarios	
Current practice	Continuation of current construction practice
Biochar	Gradual substitution of concrete with biochar-based concrete in all urban building types, up to 50% by 2050, similar to structural wood in (Mishra <i>et al</i> 2022)
Wood	Gradual substitution of current construction systems with structural wood in all urban building types, up to 50% by 2050 (Mishra <i>et al</i> 2022)
Material efficiency scenarios	
Reference	Continuation of current trends and practices
Sufficiency	Gradual reduction of floorspace per capita in new construction of all urban types up to 20% by 2050 relative to projected levels (Zhong <i>et al</i> 2021, Pauliuk <i>et al</i> 2021), by increased occupation and sharing of space consistent with decent living standards
Circular	Gradual implementation of the following material efficiency strategies in all urban building types: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Floorspace per capita reduction in new buildings (same as in the Sufficiency scenario) - Extension of expected lifetime by 90% for new buildings through improved design and durability and by 50% in existing buildings

through improved reuse and maintenance (Zhong *et al* 2021, Pauliuk *et al* 2021, Mastrucci *et al* 2024)

- Lightweighting to reduce material intensity in new construction up to 19% for aluminum and steel and 10% for concrete by 2050 (Zhong *et al* 2021, Pauliuk *et al* 2021)
- Increase the share of recycling up to 90% for steel, 95% for aluminum, and 92% for copper by 2050 (Zhong *et al* 2021)

Results

Material demand

The global demand for construction materials in urban buildings sharply increases globally under growing population and floorspace levels in the *Current practice* scenario, peaking around mid-century (Figure 1). Asia regions experience the highest material demand levels, but growth in material demand is particularly high in Africa and South America. Conversely, material demand is stable or declining in Europe and Australasia, while only slightly increasing in North America. In terms of material mass, concrete, bricks, and steel represent the largest portion of material demand across the different world regions, with some differences in the relative share of bricks and concrete reflecting diverse construction practices and building types. Material demand levels are similar in the *Biochar* scenario, with part of the concrete demand being substituted by biochar-based concrete. In contrast, the adoption of structural wood solutions in the *Wood* scenario greatly reduces material demands up to 39% globally by 2050 due to lighter-weight building structures compared to the prevailing construction practice relying on concrete, steel, and bricks.

Figure 1. Panel a: material demand in new urban construction under different material substitution scenarios. Panel b: material demand in newly constructed urban buildings in 2050 under different material substitution scenarios and comparison with 2025 levels (dashed lines) for different world regions. Note that unit scales differ by region.

Carbon storage potential

Material substitution strategies enable storing additional carbon in global urban buildings up to $0.45 \pm 0.09 \text{ kgCO}_2 \text{ yr}^{-1}$ in the Wood scenario and only $0.03 \pm 0.02 \text{ kgCO}_2 \text{ yr}^{-1}$ in the Biochar scenario by 2050

compared to current practice (Figure 2a). The total carbon storage potentials, including storage of $0.26 \text{ kgCO}_2 \text{ yr}^{-1}$ in wood-based materials under current construction practice, amount to $0.29 \text{ kgCO}_2 \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (+12%) in the Biochar scenario and $0.71 \text{ kgCO}_2 \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (+173%) in the Wood scenario (Figure 2b). Cumulative storage potentials amount to 18.5 GtCO_2 in the Current practice scenario, 20.2 GtCO_2 in the Biochar scenario, and 45.6 GtCO_2 in the Wood scenario.

Structural wood strategies entail the largest carbon storage potential due both to high storage potential per unit of material and larger amounts of bio-based materials embedded in construction. Conversely, carbon storage potential is modest with biochar-based concrete, despite the large amount of concrete demand, due to small biochar content to ensure structural resistance and relatively lower carbon storage potential per unit of material. In the first half of the century, more than half of the global storage potential is achieved in Asia (Figure 2c). After 2050, the potential shifts towards Africa due to continued increase in construction activities under population growth, while decreasing in Asia. Other regions have smaller shares and, except for South America, mostly show a declining trend over time. Residential buildings detain over 80% of the total carbon storage potential (Figure 2d), reflecting a larger share of the newly built stock relative to non-residential buildings.

Figure 2. Panel a: Additional carbon storage potential in new urban buildings worldwide due to material substitution with biochar-based concrete (biochar scenario) and structural wood (wood scenario). Ranges indicate different levels of carbon storage potential for biochar and wood, based on the literature. Panel b: Total carbon storage potential in new urban buildings worldwide under different material substitution scenarios. Panel c: average share of carbon storage potential across different world regions. Panel d: average share of carbon storage potential across residential and non-residential sectors.

GHG emission pathways

In the *Current practice* scenario, global embodied emissions for new urban buildings keep increasing through mid-century and then decline alongside material demand (Figure 3). Embodied emissions are partly offset by carbon stored in wood-based materials used in *Current practices*. The *Biochar*

scenario only minimally reduces embodied emissions as an effect of cement substitution with biochar, while storing carbon through biochar in addition to the wood-based construction in the *Current practice* scenario. Switching to structural wood in the *Wood* scenario has higher potential driven by simultaneous reduction of embodied emissions, due to lightweight and less energy-intensive construction systems, and higher storage capacity. As a result, the peak emission levels are shaved around mid-century, and net-embodied emissions are overall much lower compared to the other two scenarios. By 2050, net-embodied emissions reach 4.0 GtCO₂eq yr⁻¹ in the Biochar scenario and 1.8 GtCO₂eq yr⁻¹ in the Wood scenario. Cumulative net emissions between 2020 and 2100 sum up to 238 GtCO₂eq under Current Practices, 234 GtCO₂eq (-2%) in the Biochar scenario and 128GtCO₂eq (-46%) in the Wood scenario.

Figure 3 Projections of global embodied GHG emissions and carbon storage potential for new urban buildings under different material substitution scenarios.

Integration carbon storage with sufficiency and circular strategies

The adoption of sufficiency and circular strategies significantly reduces material demand by reducing new floorspace (*Sufficiency* scenario), narrowing material demand, delaying new construction, and enhancing material efficiency (*Circular* scenario). Total reductions in material demand compared to the *Reference* scenario amount to 28% in the *Sufficiency* scenario and 46% in the *Circular* scenario in 2050 under current practice (Figure 4a).

These material demand reductions affect both embodied emissions and carbon storage potential in the Biochar and Wood material substitution scenarios (Figure 4b). While associated with lower storage potential under reduced material demand levels, the *Circular* scenario results in the lowest values of cumulative net embodied emissions, highlighting the importance of reducing embodied emissions in the first place. Combing such embodied emission reductions with carbon storage strategies drives the largest reduction in cumulative net embodied emissions, up to 38% with biochar-based concrete and 57% with structural wood, compared to the *Reference* material efficiency scenario under Current practice (Figure 5).

Figure 4. Panel a: Projections of global material demand for new urban buildings under different material substitution scenarios and material efficiency scenarios. Panel b: Cumulative global GHG emissions and storage potential for new urban buildings under different material substitution scenarios (panels) and material efficiency scenarios (bars) between 2020 and 2100. The “x” symbols indicate net embodied emissions.

Figure 5. Difference in cumulative carbon storage and cumulative embodied net emissions relative to the Reference scenario for different material substitution and material efficiency scenarios between 2020 and 2100.

Feasibility of switching construction practice

We compare the projected biochar demand (*Biochar* scenario) and wood demand (*Wood* scenario) with relevant statistical data on current production levels to provide initial insights on upscaling implications and feasibility (Figure 4). Current production of biochar is estimated at 0.35 Mt yr⁻¹ (International Biochar Initiative 2024). Our *Biochar* scenario results in biochar demand approaching 9 Mt yr⁻¹ by mid-century, a twenty-five-fold increase compared to current total production levels. While existing studies show the potential for upscaling biochar production largely beyond these levels (Karan *et al* 2023, Sirén 2024), competition with other uses should be further considered. Wood provision in the *Wood* scenario would need to increase by a factor 1.75 compared to current total production of sawnwood to satisfy peak demand by mid-century. Also in the case of wood, uses other than building construction should be further considered on top of the projected demands. The implementation of sufficiency and circular strategies enables reduction of material demands for biochar and wood of over 40% by 2050. While in the case of biochar considerable upscaling would still be needed, for wood peak demand it would be just above the current total production levels.

Figure 6. Panel A: Global projection of biochar demand in new urban buildings when switching construction practice to biochar-based concrete under different scenarios, and comparison with current production level (International Biochar Initiative 2024). Panel B: Global projection of wood demand in new urban buildings when switching construction practice to wood-based structures under different scenarios, and comparison with current production levels of sawnwood (FAO 2026).

Discussion and conclusions

This study investigated the potential for carbon storage in future urban building scenarios using biochar-based concrete and structural wood. Our results indicate that implementing structural wood in 50% of new urban buildings by 2050 is effective both in reducing embodied emissions and in storing carbon, leading to 46% lower net cumulative GHG emissions compared to a reference scenario. Biochar-based concrete exhibits more limited carbon storage potential despite higher material deployment, primarily due to the constrained share of biochar, with only 2% reduction in net cumulative GHG emissions relative to a reference scenario. Sufficiency and circular strategies substantially lower material demand across all scenarios and, despite trade-offs with storage potential, result in the largest reductions in net cumulative GHG emissions, up to 57% with structural wood and 38% with biochar-based concrete.

Overall, these findings are in line with existing research on carbon storage in the built environment, but with some important differences. The additional carbon storage potential of switching construction practice to structural wood in 50% of new urban buildings has an average value of 0.34 GtCO₂ yr⁻¹ over the period 2020-2100, close to the upper limit of the range 0.1 -0.3 GtCO₂ yr⁻¹ provided in (Rodríguez Mendez *et al* 2024). The cumulative emission savings in our Wood

scenario (110 GtCO₂) is higher than in the corresponding scenario in (Mishra *et al* 2022), implementing wood in 50% of new urban buildings worldwide, in absolute terms (71 GtCO₂). Cumulative emission reductions are however similar in relative terms, namely 46% in our study and 51% in (Mishra *et al* 2022). A major difference between the two studies lies in the projected trends of carbon storage through wood construction. While the study by (Mishra *et al* 2022) shows a continuous growth in the storage potential driven by wood implementation, our study present a peak around mid-century and subsequent decline, following a slow down in global population growth resulting in lower new construction and material demand levels. This trend is consistent with other studies of global wood demand (Gingrich *et al* 2025). Being literature very sparse on the carbon storage potential in buildings, only limited comparison is possible. Previous studies (Rodriguez Mendez *et al* 2024) report a storage potential of 0.2-0.3 GtCO₂ yr⁻¹ through biochar-based cement in buildings construction. We found a much lower potential of 0.02 GtCO₂ yr⁻¹, average in the period 2020-2100, likely due to the limitations in embedding biochar in concrete to ensure minimum structural resistance. On the other hand, this is likely a conservative value as we only consider biochar-based concrete, while not accounting for other cement-based materials, such as plaster and mortar, where biochar could be embedded.

This study advances global research on carbon storage potentials in buildings in several ways. While previous research has primarily focused on carbon storage in wood (Mishra *et al* 2022, Gingrich *et al* 2025), we expand the scope by including biochar-based concrete, an alternative, yet highly debated, structural material. We also enhance earlier assessments of storage potentials (Van Roijen *et al* 2025) through the incorporation of future urbanization dynamics and building stock evolution. By explicitly accounting for building stock turnover, we provide an internally consistent assessment of material inflows, embodied emissions, and carbon storage, further combined with sufficiency and circularity considerations. Together, these advances enable a more comprehensive and robust evaluation of net GHG emission trajectories associated with embodied carbon reduction and storage strategies, particularly in the context of future urbanization pathways relevant for decision-making and resource-efficient decarbonization.

Comparisons with current material production levels in our study highlight the need for substantial upscaling to meet projected demand, by up to a factor of 25 for biochar and 1.75 for wood. The limited availability of bio-based materials for use in construction is a widely discussed concern in the literature (IPCC 2022a). A marked increase in forest harvests driven by expanding wood markets has raised concerns about potentially undermining future forest-based climate mitigation and biodiversity conservation (Ceccherini *et al* 2020). Demand-side sufficiency and circular strategies can further improve the feasibility of material substitutions by reducing material demand and slowing material cycles through extended product lifetimes, as illustrated in our analysis. On the supply side, improved supply-chain management, reducing carbon leakage, wood cascading and closing bio-based material loops are equally important (Jarre *et al* 2020). Management approaches that enable the production of construction timber alongside biomass for energy and other uses could be developed within the agriculture and forestry sectors, potentially providing multiple co-benefits (Nabuurs *et al* 2017).

Future modelling efforts should better account for these cross-sectoral interactions, competitions and synergies across different biomass uses, including construction, energy, and food systems, as well as impacts on forest ecosystems to ensure that increased use of bio-based materials does not exceed ecological limits (IPCC 2022a). At present, however, building and land-use models remain largely disconnected and tend to overlook these interactions, with only a limited number of studies explicitly linking wood-based construction and land-use dynamics (Mishra *et al* 2022, Gingrich *et al* 2025). Biochar, for example, is also applied to cropland to enhance soil fertility and crop yields (Javadi *et al* 2024, Li *et al* 2024, Joseph *et al* 2021) (Joseph *et al* 2021, Li *et al* 2024), highlighting a competing demand between its use in the agricultural sector and emerging applications in building materials. At the same time, natural disturbances (Grünig *et al* 2026, van Lierop *et al* 2015), such as wildfires and insect outbreaks, introduce additional uncertainty into the supply of construction wood. Additional efforts are therefore required to better integrate land-use, energy system, and

building sector modelling within a comprehensive carbon accounting framework, in order to capture cross-sectoral interactions and system-wide implications (Mastrucci *et al* 2023, Churkina *et al* 2020). Greater attention is needed to land-use implications, including biodiversity and nature conservation, alongside land-use change and biogenic emissions, to capture the broader environmental consequences of shifting construction practices. Economic feasibility is also critical, given competing uses of biomass and other resources (Muscat *et al* 2020), and should be systematically incorporated into future analyses, along with socio-economic implications, such as employment and distributional effects (Howard *et al* 2021). Finally, stronger integration with the energy supply sector is necessary to position construction material strategies within broader decarbonization pathways (Pauliuk *et al* 2017).

In this study, we focused on a limited set of bio-based structural materials to investigate carbon storage potential in global urban buildings. Future assessments should encompass a broader range of materials with a whole life-cycle approach. Non-structural bio-based construction materials, including bio-based panels and insulation, should be included for more comprehensive analysis. Use of local fast-growing bio-based materials is promising both in building renovation, e.g. straw and cork, and new building construction, e.g. bamboo, across different world locations (Göswein *et al* 2026, Carcassi *et al* 2022), requiring region-specific analysis. Carbon storage in mineral materials, including cement carbonation (Xi *et al* 2016, Van Roijen *et al* 2025), should be further explored and compared with bio-based solutions in future building scenarios. While we focus here on exogenous uptake rates for material substitution, future scenario work should account for more realistic adoption dynamics, considering competition across sectors, market and price dynamics, and constraints on forestry and land-use side, e.g. nature conservation. Despite these limitations, the scenarios developed in this study can provide a strong starting point for more integrated assessments on the carbon storage potential in the global urban building sector to effectively support sustainability and climate mitigation strategies.

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